
The challenges of regulating interoperability

*Analysing Apple's request-based approach
under the Digital Markets Act*

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report highlights the hurdles facing competing developers seeking interoperability with Apple's iOS and iPadOS platforms under the EU Digital Markets Act (DMA). It sheds light on the European Commission (EC)'s latest framework for software and hardware interoperability specified in two decisions issued in March 2025.

In particular, the report elaborates on the shortcomings of Apple's request-based approach in relation to effective interoperability. Apple's model requires developers to navigate account creation, fees, detailed requests, internal review, and potentially long implementation timelines.

The report argues that while the regulatory framework issued by the EC on interoperability represents progress by imposing transparency and due process obligations on Apple, governance issues will arise in the future. Therefore, the report calls for open standards, transparent procedures, and stronger regulatory enforcement so that Free Software developers can participate on fairer terms within the mobile ecosystem.

APPLE AND THE CHALLENGES OF REGULATING INTEROPERABILITY

Apple is one of the largest tech companies in the world. Due to its market power in Europe, the company is considered a “gatekeeper” under the Digital Markets Act (DMA), a law designed to regulate digital competition. Under the DMA, Apple is required to provide “free-of-charge” interoperability for the features and functionalities controlled by its mobile operating systems (iOS and iPadOS). This means allowing users and third party developers to install and remove apps freely and use alternative app stores, and that developers be able to connect their apps to important software and hardware features instead of being blocked at the platform’s door.

At the Free Software Foundation Europe (FSFE), we believe this is an opportunity for Free Software developers to finally compete with gatekeepers’ services on a level playing field. Free Software developers have the right to develop alternatives that compete fairly with operating systems like iOS and iPadOs, that have been closed ecosystems since their inception. The DMA now offers users the possibilities to finally be able to choose alternative and Free Software app stores, choose payment systems or tuninstall and install apps in an unfettered way (“side-loading”).

Interoperability and Device Neutrality

For Free Software, the possibility to get access to gatekeepers’ services and features via interoperability rights, and installing and uninstalling software in mobile devices, is directly tied to [Device Neutrality](#): the idea that you should be free to run the software you want on the devices you own, without being locked into one vendor’s ecosystem. Free Software projects should have the same access to data and interfaces as proprietary competitors.

This is why, from the very beginning of the legislative process, we have been advocating for an interpretation and enforcement of the DMA that

empowers smaller Free Software developers, so they can compete on an equal footing with gatekeepers' own services and finally offer real alternatives.

Making Article 6(7) of the DMA Free-Software-developer friendly is crucial for Device Neutrality: it obliges gatekeepers to provide effective interoperability with, and access to, the software and hardware features of designated operating systems such as iOS and iPadOS. In practical terms, this means that developers must be able to access the same operating-system-controlled features that the gatekeeper's own services use, instead of being kept on the outside looking in.

Interoperability regulation in practice

When the DMA entered into force, we expected gatekeepers like Apple to open up their platforms by publishing APIs, providing clear and accessible documentation, and giving all developers the same technical hooks that Apple's own services enjoy – interoperability by default, not by exception.

Instead, some gatekeepers (e.g. Apple and Google) set up request-based systems. Each developer must individually ask for access to a specific feature and then wait while Apple decides whether that feature is “in scope”, turning a legal right into a case-by-case permission.

This restrictive approach towards interoperability prompted the European Commission to regulate Apple. As we explain further in this report, the best solution would be an approach that incorporates “interoperability-by-design”. Progress has been made through the [Commission's specification decision](#), though this should not obscure the fact that Apple's discretionary power over interoperability access remains intact.

This analysis will focus on Apple's compliance approach, since it is at this moment the most complex one among the gatekeepers.

How a developer must request interoperability (step-by-step)

A developer, who develops an app or a system that needs to interoperate with features and functionalities of iOS and iPadOS, must go through several steps:

1. **Sign a contract with Apple and pay to enter the system**
As a starter, the developer must create an Apple developer account, which costs, in 2026, 99 USD per year.
2. **Submit a detailed request form**
Through Apple's online form, the developer must: (a) describe the feature or functionality needed, and explain why Apple's involvement is required to ensure interoperability; (b) provide details about the product that will use the feature and where it is offered; (c) indicate whether alternative solutions were considered, and set confidentiality preferences; and (d) add any further technical or contextual information Apple requests.
3. **Wait up to 20 working days for Apple's first assessment**
Apple then has up to 20 working days to decide; (i) whether the request can proceed; (ii) whether Apple claims an existing solution already covers it; (iii) or whether the request is rejected as "out of scope".
4. **Follow an internal review and/or conciliation procedure**
If Apple rejects a request on technical grounds the developer can ask for:
 - (a) an **internal review** by Apple's Interoperability Request Review Board (IRRB), and
 - (b) if still dissatisfied, an external, **non-binding technical expert review** through a conciliation process run by independent conciliators.
5. **Face Apple's control over what counts as "in scope"**
Even with internal review and conciliation, Apple's initial classification of whether a feature is "controlled by" or "accessed via" the operating system still shapes the entire process. Only decisions based on certain technical grounds can go into internal review and conciliation, while broader questions (such as whether something is a "feature" under Article 6(7) at all) may be excluded from these mechanisms. This preserves significant discretion for Apple and forces developers to argue against Apple's own technical framing before they can benefit from independent technical scrutiny.

6. Potentially wait up to 24 months for implementation

If Apple ultimately accepts the request and no solution already exists, it gives itself up to 24 months to develop and ship the interoperability measure, depending on the “technical complexity” of the request, a complexity that Apple itself evaluates. For simple requests, Apple has 6 months to develop and release the solution to third party developers. For “mild” requests, Apple has 12 months, and 18 for “complex” requests. In any case, the whole process, from the request, should last a maximum of 24 months. This means that, even in the best-case scenario, the first full results of the process will only become visible around 2027, and only for developers who can afford to wait that long and keep paying to stay in the system.

Figure 1: Timeline proposed by the European Commission to regulate Apple’s interoperability requests. Source: European Commission.

Apple’s approach vs “interoperability by design”

This regulatory process was triggered by the European Commission, which opened the [specification case DMA.100204](#) to ensure Apple would follow a common, non-discriminatory approach for all requests, set clear timelines for granting or denying interoperability, and publish a public tracker listing these requests and Apple’s responses. We do recognise that this was an important step for more transparency and accountability, but we have

argued that this restrictive approach cannot replace “interoperability by design”: open, well-documented technical specifications to features and functionalities available to everyone, without developers having to ask gatekeepers for permission feature by feature. The FSFE and other civil society organisations [warned that this reactive model undermines developer agency and gives Apple wide discretion to accept, delay, or reject requests.](#)

WHAT APPLE'S INTEROPERABILITY TRACKER REVEALS

The [published tracker](#) (for access to which an Apple account is required) includes several requests that directly affect developers and competitors and illustrate how Apple's interpretation of Article 6(7) can hamper the DMA in practice.

As of March 22, 2026, Apple had received 56 interoperability requests under Article 6(7) of the DMA since May 2025. The vast majority, 43 requests (76.8%), have been closed, while 12 (21.4%) were actively progressing through Phase III (technical assessment), and 1 (1.8%) was still in Phase I (eligibility review). No requests were at the time of the analysis in Phase II. Of the 43 closed cases, 27 (62.8% of closed) are marked fully confidential, meaning Apple's communications are withheld from public view and one cannot determine their outcome.

Of the remaining 16 publicly disclosed closures, not a single one resulted in Apple developing a new interoperability solution at the time of the analysis: 10 were denied on "technical grounds", and 2 were denied with Apple citing an "existing solution"; 3 were rejected as "out of scope or invalid" (reclassified as bug reports, outside Article 6(7) scope, or not valid interoperability requests). For this initial sample, across all publicly visible outcomes, Apple has yet to develop a single new interoperability solution in response to these DMA requests.

Apple DMA Art. 6(7) Interoperability Requests

Figure 2. Interoperability requests received by Apple under Art. 6(7) DMA until 22.03.2026

Building on this overview, we analysed some of the most striking requests and rejections in order to highlight the main patterns and concerns emerging from Apple's review process.

- **Gatekeeping power over access to the interoperability request form:** As opposed to other gatekeepers who keep the interoperability request open without the need for an online account (e.g. [Microsoft](#)), Apple's request for interoperability form is only accessible with an Apple Account and users registered as Apple developers. It means, the developer should enter in an agreement, accept the terms and conditions and pay 99 USD per year to have access to the interoperability request, which is required by the DMA to be free-of-charge. Our survey¹ collected a report of a developer account being deleted by Apple, and after that the developer could not access the interoperability request any more.
- **Denying access to "just-in-time compilation":** One Free Software terminal-like app requested access to the Just-In-Time (JIT) compilation API already used by Safari, arguing that its technical

1 More information on the [DMA Interoperability Survey](#) developed by the FSFE can be found below in the section "Call for action".

needs are identical to browsers: securely executing downloaded code inside a sandbox. Apple rejected the request by asserting that JIT for non-browser apps is not a feature “accessed or controlled by iOS”, even though JIT clearly exists on the platform and is enabled for Apple’s own browser. As the Commission has stated, if interoperability were to be limited to those services and hardware that a gatekeeper already offers, the gatekeeper would enjoy a first-mover advantage for every use case relying on reserved iOS or iPadOS features, leaving little room for innovation (§ 28 DMA.100204). Apple should allow the interoperability solution to be used for innovative and potentially unforeseen use cases. Once the interoperability solution has been implemented and released in iOS or iPadOS, Apple should not restrict the types or use cases of the service or hardware that uses the interoperability solution at the iOS or iPadOS platform level. There should be no restrictions that result in an inability for any developer to use the interoperability solution for any use case. In particular, there should be no policy restrictions on the use case or developer (§ 128 DMA.100204)

- **Documentation’s contradiction:** In another case, a developer asked for support for FIDO tokens in wallet passes and for access to the VAS NFC protocol used by Apple Wallet. Apple claimed that “FIDO token support and the NFC element of Apple Wallet are not features that are accessed or controlled via iOS or iPadOS.” Yet [Apple’s own documentation states](#) that “Adding NFC to a Pass requires a special entitlement issued by Apple”, an OS-level permission gate that clearly shows OS control over NFC access. This contradicts Apple’s claim and highlights how its interpretation of “not controlled by the OS” can be used to deny interoperability. In this case, as also recognised by the Commission, in a context characterised by information asymmetry and imbalance in bargaining power, a request-based process may allow the gatekeeper, in this case Apple, to undermine the effectiveness of access rights to the developers (§ 292 DMA.100204), resulting in the impossibility for third party developers to even access the remedies foreseen by the process, because Apple retains complete control over the request-based process and its outcome (i.e. whether, when and how interoperability will be provided), in a context where the gatekeeper may have incentives to refuse, delay,

or restrict the provision of interoperability to competitors or potential competitors (§ 105 DMA.100204).

- **Rejecting interoperability to implemented features in iOS:** A project requested Bluetooth Low Energy (LE) Audio support for headphones, needed to connect research devices that rely on the LE Audio standard. Apple responded that the requested feature is “not available to or used by Apple’s hardware and/or services”, even though the broader Bluetooth Low Energy stack is [implemented in iOS](#) and LE Audio [is supported on competing platforms such as Android](#). This restrictive approach is not supported by the Commission, which has stated that by granting access strictly to what Apple itself already ships and markets, the company avoids enabling interoperability that would benefit independent research and Free Software ecosystems. As the Commission stated, innovation can only take place if interoperability is not limited to a select group of beneficiaries, apps or use cases. In particular, it cannot be left to the discretion of the gatekeeper to decide which third parties, apps, products and use cases can benefit from the interoperability (§ 56 DMA.100204).
- **Rejection of alternatives to Apple’s own services.** Two different developers requested interoperability for push notifications that do not rely solely on the Apple Push Notification Service (APNS). Their goal is to support decentralised or user-controlled notification servers. In simple terms, they want to be able to send notifications to iOS and iPadOS users without having to go through Apple’s servers. Apple rejected both requests, arguing that maintaining persistent connections, a function required to send such notifications, is purely an “operating system” feature, not something used by Apple’s own services. The company also claimed that the existing APNS system is already open to all developers. However, this interpretation overlooks the DMA’s purpose, which is to ensure genuine alternatives to Apple’s default, vertically integrated services rather than reinforce their exclusivity. If interoperability were to be limited to those services and hardware that a gatekeeper already offers, the gatekeeper would enjoy a first-mover advantage for every use case relying on reserved iOS or iPadOS features, leaving little room for innovation (§ 58 DMA.100204). Apple should indeed allow the

interoperability solution to be used for innovative and potentially unforeseen use cases (§ 298 DMA.100204).

Breakdown of Closed Requests by Apple under DMA Art. 6(7)

Figure 3. Status of the interoperability requests received by Apple under Art. 6(7) DMA until 22.03.2026

WHY DOES THIS MATTER FOR FREE SOFTWARE DEVELOPERS?

The FSFE has repeatedly stressed that the DMA must not become an industry-only playground dominated by negotiations between a handful of large corporations. Many interoperability requests in Apple's tracker come from individual developers, research projects, and small companies building Free Software that cannot afford lengthy administrative, legal and conciliatory procedures or repeated rejections. For them, each refusal based on a formalistic reading of "not controlled by iOS" or "not used by Apple hardware" is a concrete barrier to reaching users on dominant mobile platforms.

- **Barriers in the request-based model.** The current request-based system is slow and puts too much work on developers. Each developer must prove that a feature is "used by Apple," rather than Apple being required to make access fair and effective. Apple's own system designs and unclear definitions let it decide what counts under the DMA, limiting what smaller projects can do. This goes against the idea of interoperability by design, where open APIs and documentation are available from the start – so anyone can build tools and services.
- **Questionable compliance with the DMA *free of charge* provision.** Apple's requirements of signing a contract with terms and conditions, forcing developers to have a developer account and paying a fee of, at least, 99 USD per year just to submit an interoperability request seem hard to justify. Article 6(7) of the DMA clearly says that access to interoperability measures must be *free of charge*.
- **Complex and lengthy conciliation mechanisms.** The internal review and the conciliation mechanisms are important safeguards that can correct some of Apple's decisions. However, they add additional layers (strict deadlines to appeal, written submissions,

expert review) that require time, legal and technical knowledge, and persistence. For smaller and Free Software developers, this extra complexity can make it difficult to actually use these venues. These mechanisms show that developers are not entirely without recourse. But they also underlines our concerns: Apple still retains wide discretion in defining the scope and technical framing of requests.

- **Apple’s discretion and technical control.** Even with the remedies of the latest European Commission specification decision (DMA.100204), Apple still decides how wide or narrow each request can be and what technical rules apply. As a result, developers remain dependent on Apple’s interpretation. A clear pattern has emerged: when a feature would help alternative clients, devices, or Free Software compete with Apple’s own products, Apple often claims that the feature “isn’t controlled by iOS” or “doesn’t apply to Apple hardware.”

GOVERNANCE THAT WORKS BEYOND BIG TECH

A fair DMA needs governance that works for more than just big industry players. If compliance and enforcement are driven only by large companies and their lawyers, the DMA risks becoming an industry-focused framework that leaves out exactly the smaller, community-driven, and non-profit developers who build alternatives to gatekeepers' services. For these actors, rules and procedures must be simple, predictable, and understandable without a legal department: clear obligations, open technical specifications, and processes that do not require months of correspondence or expert counsel just to request interoperability.

The EU's vs the UK's regulatory approach

While the EU's DMA is already a significant step forward compared to most of the world, where similar rules do not yet exist, it should still be seen as a starting point rather than the final answer. Its value will depend on how it is enforced in practice and whether regulators keep pushing for interoperability by design instead of accepting a slow, request-driven model controlled by gatekeepers.

The UK's approach under the Digital Markets Competition and Consumers Act (DMCCA) raises a different set of concerns. Instead of imposing binding interoperability obligations comparable to Article 6(7) DMA, the UK Competition Market Authority (CMA) is currently relying on voluntary commitments proposed by Apple. The legal status of these commitments is not entirely clear, as the DMCCA does not explicitly provide a framework for this type of arrangement. This creates a degree of uncertainty as to their enforceability and the consequences of non-compliance.

Together with other civil society organisations, we have highlighted that these UK commitments leave Apple broad discretion to define what is in scope, when to refuse access, and how far interoperability extends, without any equivalent to the DMA's clear, free-of-charge access right. At the same time, the experience under Article 6(7) DMA shows that even a binding obligation can be narrowed in practice when Apple implements it through restrictive, request-based processes.

In practice, this means that developers in both jurisdictions face significant barriers: in the UK, because interoperability remains dependent on Apple's internal policies and discretion from the outset; and in the EU, because a formally guaranteed right risks being reduced to a case-by-case permission system. The difference, however, is that in the EU developers can at least rely on binding legal obligations and a formal enforcement framework to challenge restrictive or non-compliant practices, something that remains unclear under the UK's current commitments-based approach.

Short run: interoperability access should be effective and free of charge

In the short term, equal and fair access rights for all developers are crucial for a developer-friendly enforcement of the DMA. Until now, gatekeepers have been leading the implementation of the interoperability provision and of the DMA more generally. The specification decision issued by the Commission on interoperability is a good step forward, but at the same time, Apple has still complete discretionary power on granting interoperability rights and third party developers need to pay, accept the terms and conditions of an account, wait up to 24 months, and risk being trapped in lengthy legal battles.

Long run: open standards are key

In the long term, shared governance is essential: not only regulators but also affected developers, users and civil society should have a voice in how interoperability is designed, monitored, and enforced. Free Software, with its traditions of [open standards](#) and community oversight, shows that the interoperability solutions emerging under the DMA can be democratically governed, supporting digital commons, rather than being left to bilateral deals between gatekeepers and only their biggest competitors.

CALL FOR ACTION

HELP US DOCUMENT, HELP US ACT

That is why at the FSFE we have not been standing still, but immediately took action by launching the [DMA interoperability survey](#), a tool to collect first-hand experiences from developers requesting interoperability from gatekeepers. We want to make sure that developers who do not have large legal teams behind them can have their voices heard, so that we can bring evidence to the European Commission, highlight non-compliance, empower smaller developers, and ensure that the DMA is enforced in a developer-friendly way.

The FSFE will continue to monitor DMA enforcement and challenge interpretations that leave Free Software developers and users behind. To do this effectively, we need solid, real-world evidence of how interoperability (or the lack of it) affects developers working with gatekeepers' platforms.

If you are a developer who has requested access to software or hardware features under Article 6(7) DMA from any of the gatekeepers, or would like to do so but are discouraged by the process, please fill out our interoperability survey and share your experience.

[FILL OUT THE SURVEY NOW](#)

For everyone who cares about Device Neutrality and software freedom, your support makes this work possible. Monitoring gatekeepers, analysing complex legal and technical documents, and intervening in regulatory processes requires sustained, independent resources. Please [become an FSFE supporter](#), so that we can keep pushing the DMA towards genuine interoperability by design and ensure that Free Software developers of all sizes can finally compete on equal terms, making sure that by [2048 everyone will have the right to install any software in any device](#).

The Free Software Foundation Europe (FSFE) is a charity that empowers users to control technology. Software is deeply involved in all aspects of our lives; it is important that this technology empowers rather than restricts us. Free Software gives everybody the rights to use, understand, adapt and share software. These rights help support other fundamental freedoms like freedom of speech, press and privacy.

The FSFE was founded in 2001 as a non-profit, non-governmental organisation and network that is itself part of a global network of people with common goals and visions. The FSFE is supported by its members from all over Europe and has regional chapters in eleven countries. The central component of the FSFE's work is keeping the legal, political, and social base of Free Software strong, secure and free of particular interests.

